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IMPLEMENTATION OF TOOLS FOR IMPROVEMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF WORK PROCESSES WITH CAD SOFTWARE AND SPREADSHEETS FOR THE SUBJECT TECHNOLOGY PROJECTS WORKSHOP

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Abstract

Future architects must be able to choose and calculate the facilities, the construction system and the structural system of the building they design, integrating these disciplines into the architectural context of the buildings and acquiring a commitment to functionality, economy, aesthetics and environmental balance. This is why the Technology Projects Workshop subject in the 5th year of the Architecture degree has the following learning objectives:

- Apply specific technical regulations on technical disciplines in buildings.
- Plan, design, size and calculate the facilities, construction system and structural system.
- Develop capabilities and skills to be able to integrate technical disciplines and their influence on architectural design through design.

The workflow in architectural education with the integration of computer tools in design processes has been an area of growing interest and relevance [1 y 2]. In an increasingly digital world, understanding how these tools affect work processes is essential to prepare future architects for the challenges of contemporary design linked to the development of parametric architecture [3 y 4]. In this context, the present study presents a proposal for the introduction of tutorials to improve the processes of using spreadsheet tools integrated with CAD, BIM and GIS software to improve the efficiency and quality of the work developed by students in the subject:

1) AutoCAD, Structural Code and Excel (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Screenshots of the Autocad, Structural code and Excel tutorial.

2) AutoCAD: printing with precision (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Screenshots from the Autocad tutorial: Printing with precision.

3) Automated Batch Renaming in AutoCAD (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Tutorial Screenshots: Automated Batch Renaming in AutoCAD.

4) Express management of cadastral data using Excel (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Screenshots of the tutorial: Express management of cadastral data using Excel.

5) Automate the climate zone assignment of our projects using Excel (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Tutorial Screenshots: Automate Climate Zone Assignment.

6) Work with QGIS and open data for the urban parameters of the project (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Screenshots of the tutorial: Working with QGIS and open data.

Several studies have highlighted how these tools contribute to three-dimensional visualization, efficient collaboration and data analysis in advanced architectural projects [5 y 6]. These studies suggest that the appropriate use of digital tools can improve creativity, problem solving, and preparation for the practical challenges of the profession [7 y 8]. However, it is also crucial to recognize the challenges and limitations associated with implementing these tools. These may include resistance to change, need for additional training, and the possibility of overreliance on technology [9].

In conclusion, the Implementation of tools to improve and optimize work processes with CAD, GIS, BIM and spreadsheet software for the Technology Projects Workshop subject is not only viable, but also highly beneficial, as it emerges as a strategy promising to enrich architectural training, optimizing work processes and improving the use made of the resources and possibilities of these applications. Although challenges have been identified, the potential benefits in terms of efficiency and design quality support the continued exploration and adaptation of these technologies in the educational field. Highlighting its importance for the development of practical and theoretical skills in future architects.

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